

A TREND ANALYSIS OF GOODS AND SERVICE TAX COLLECTION IN INDIA SINCE 2016 AND TAX SLABS AMENDMENTS OF 2025

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Abstract

A complex taxation system sometimes leads to tax evasion. Easy and simple indirect tax structure makes life easy for businessmen. All the intermediaries between manufacturers and retailers face very less problems when tax policies are clear and without ambiguities. In India, indirect tax overhaul took place in July 2017 through Goods and Service Tax which removed the cascading effect of taxation. This indirect tax revamp helped every stakeholder to be in a win-win situation. The Government of India has also started collecting whopping amounts through GST.

The new GST regime has not just increased government revenue but the compliance from sellers has also increased. The present study tried to understand GST structure and analyzed the trends in GST tax collection since July 2017. Researcher have also discussed the recent amendments done in GST slabs in September 2025. Secondary data has been used for the study.

Keywords- *Indirect tax, Goods and Service Tax, GST council, revamp, cascading effect*

Introduction

The Indian government was collecting indirect taxes by levying different types of taxes. Before July 2017, the rate and types of taxes varied in central, state and union territories. Central and state governments had their separate taxation system. Some of the taxes were, Value Added tax (VAT), Excise duty, service tax, entertainment tax etc. It was complex because of the variety of taxes. Transporting goods from one state to another was cumbersome in the earlier taxation regime. The government took a decision to revamp indirect tax structure for removing cascading effects in the taxation. India adopted a new indirect tax system i.e. Goods and Service

Tax (GST) in July 2017. Tobacco, alcohol, petrol and petroleum products are excluded from GST.

Prime Minister Narendra Modi said, GST is a Good and Simple Tax but Mr. Rahul Gandhi said it is a Gabbar Singh Tax. The Council of the GST said that GST made compliance easy. Government has divided the GST in three different parts i.e. CGST (Central Goods and Service Tax), SGST (State Goods and Service Tax), IGST (Integrated Goods and Service Tax) and UTGST (Union Territory Goods and Services Tax). Under GST, 0%, 5%, 12%, 18%, 28% and 40% of these six slabs were made for various goods and services. Some of the experts from various industries have appreciated this taxation overhaul and some have criticized it too. One thing we must underscore about GST is that the amount collected through GST is almost doubled from Rs. 11.36 lakh crore in 2020-21 to Rs. 22.08 lakh crore in 2024-25. It means the GST collection was doubled within the span of four years. The highest GST amount collected in a month was Rs. 2.37 lakh crore in April 2025, the growth was 12.06% as compared to the same month of last year. The GST collection has shown upward trend in almost all the years except COVID year 2020-21 where trend was downward.

Objectives-

1. To understand the structure of GST in India.
2. To analyze the year wise trend in the GST collection.
3. To find out recent amendments in the GST slabs in India.

Research Methodology

The data used for this study is secondary and compiled from government reports, and authentic websites, newspapers etc. Also refer books and research papers published in national and international research journals. Researcher also referred to and used the data and information published by the Press information Bureau, Ministry of finance and GST council. Trend analysis of the data has been done with the help of formula.

Literature Review

Omprakash Gupta, Payal Rajpoot & Narsingh Kumar Soni (2024) in their research paper entitled “A Comprehensive Analysis of Goods and Service Tax (GST) in India” have tried to study the impact of GST on construction industry, to ascertain the growth after implementing GST and to see whether indirect tax has been increased after GST. The researchers collected responses from 100 respondents and 60 percent of them have said that GST significantly impacted the construction industry. Their study also found that indirect tax collection has

increased after GST implementation. As far as growth is concerned, the authors have mentioned in their study that the positive growth has been noticed after GST.

Dr. Neeta Deepaware & Dr. Shivangi Dwivedi (2022) in their paper entitled “GST in India: Its Impact on Indian Economy” have found that the GST has impacted the Indian economy. They have also studied and found that the GST has impacted on almost all the sectors and various types of businesses.

Dr. Shinde Bhausaheb Nanasaheb & Dr. Dhotre Avinash Changdeo (2025) in their research paper entitled “Recent Changes in GST for Simplification of GST Compliance in India: An Overview” have highlighted the year wise history of GST starting from the year 2000 until the launch of GST in 2021. Authors have said that GST is a destination-based tax and they have provided a list of various taxes in India before GST. The important difference they have articulated in their study is an old return filing system and new simplified return filing system.

A. Phani Bhushan & Dr. S. Lakshmi Tulasi Devi (2024) in their research paper entitled “The Rudimentary Lessons of GST Implementation in India” have tried to accentuate two important stakeholders i.e. the taxpayers and tax administrators. Three important T’s have been underscored trust, transparency and technology which determine the relationship between taxpayers and tax administrators. Researchers of this paper gave much emphasis on ease of doing business. They have also discussed how the GST administrative framework will help in nation building.

Table- 1
Year wise GST collection since 2017-18

Year	GST Collection (in ₹ Crore)	Trend Analysis
FY 2017–18	7,40,650	-----
FY 2018–19	11,77,368	100
FY 2019–20	12,22,116	104 %
FY 2020–21	11,36,805	97 %
FY 2021–22	14,83,291	126 %
FY 2022–23	18,07,680	154 %
FY 2023–24	20,18,249	171 %

Fy 2024-25	₹ 22,08,861	188 %
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Source- Government of India, Press information Bureau (PIB) & tatanexarc.com/msme/gst-collection-monthly-and-yearly-trends

The table-1 indicates the trend of GST collection since July 2017. The changes in the GST collection amount can be divided into three periods i.e. pre covid, during and post COVID-19. 2017-18, 2018-19 and 2019-20 were pre covid years as well as starting years of the GST. In these years, the GST collection was in a transition period. The GST collected in the first nine months of 2017-18 was 7,40,650 crores, 11,77,368 crores was in 2018-19 and 12,22,116 crores was in the year 2019-20.

During covid, the GST collection dropped to 11,36,805 crores in the year 2020-21 and again rose to Rs. 14,83,291 crores in the year 2021-22. The GST collection started to recover in the year 2022-23 and it was 18,07,680 crores. Important years which need to be underscored i.e. 2023-24 and 2024-25 where in GST achieved whopping increments. 20,18,249 crore and 22,08,861 crores were the recent two years collection. Therefore, except covid years, GST collections have shown incremental growth which is significant.

Diagram-1

Year wise GST collection trend since 2017-18

Table-2**Current GST Tax Rate Vs New GST Tax Rate amended in Sept 2025**

With the help of table 2, we will be able to understand the new tax rate and the things get cheaper at the revised rate.

Goods and Services	Old Rate	New Rate
Daily Essentials- Milk, Bread, Curd, etc.	Nil	Nil
Hair Oil, Shampoo, Toiletries, etc.	18%	5%
Butter, Ghee, and Cheese	12%	5%
Personal Health & Life Insurance	18%	Nil
Air Conditioners	28%	18%
Tv & Refrigerator	28%	18%
Small Cars Below 1200cc	28%	18%
Bikes Below 350cc	28%	18%
Tableware, Kitchenware, Utensils & Bamboo Furniture	12%	5%
Stationery Items- Pencils, Charts, Globes, Exercise Books & Notebooks	12%	5%
Cement	28%	18%
Hotel Tariffs Up To ₹7500	12%	5%
Agriculture Machinery- Tractors, Drip Irrigation Systems, Sprinklers, etc.	12%	5%
Aerated and Sugary Beverages, Caffeinated Beverages	28%	40%
Luxury Cars and Premium Bikes	28%	40%
Tobacco, Cigarettes, and Other Sin Goods	28%	40%

Source- Ministry of Finance <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=2163555>

56th GST council meeting was conducted on 3rd and 4th September 2025 wherein several Next Generation Reforms were made by members of the committee. GST rates were rationalized and unified into three slabs from earlier six slabs. Some of the highlighted decisions are zero tax on medical insurance which was previously 18% on the premium. This is a big relief for the insurance purchasers. There are many positive changes done by the GST council in taxation which saves common man's money and that saved money can be utilized for some more purchases.

Union finance minister Smt. Nirmala Sitharaman said, due to reduced GST on certain products from 22th September 2025, people will have 2 lakh crores more rupees in their hands to spend.

Conclusion

Indirect tax is an important source of revenue for the government. Indians were grappling with complex tax structures that existed for the last many decades. Any government cannot increase the tax rate in a haphazard manner, because it requires detailed discussion and brainstorming amongst experts and concerned government representatives. The decision of the GST was pending for several years. The government realized that the decision was right because it started getting a good amount of indirect tax through GST. Year wise GST collection with the trend has been shown in present study. All those amounts glaringly shows us the whopping amounts collected through goods and service tax since 2017. The trend shows that except Covid period, the GST collection was astonishing.

Another important event in the sphere of GST happened in Sept 2025, when the GST council revised the tax slabs for most goods and services. The government should always take a review of tax rates and see whether tax rationalization is needed. Basic goods which are regularly required to lower income people should be free from tax. Making insurance premium free of tax is a commendable decision taken by the GST council.

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